

Materials Management Practices, Problems, and Solutions on SMES's Building Construction Sites in Mogadishu.

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Abstract.

The purpose of the thesis was to investigate, assess, and establish the material management practices, problems, and solutions on the building construction sites in Somalia. Mixed research method was used because it combines quantitative and qualitative research methods, procedures, approaches, ideas, or language into a single study. The sample size for this study was determined to be 100. The questionnaire was used for this research study to ensure simplicity and accuracy.

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The questionnaire was used for this research study to ensure simplicity and accuracy. A random sampling process will be used to choose the sample frame. About 100 questionnaires were sent to different construction companies in Somalia. The findings indicates that the management of building materials, as well known, plays an essential role in boosting the productivity of construction projects. Somalia currently does not have a well-developed system for managing building materials and construction materials. Due to the complexities of the construction industry, some projects have suffered material and financial losses because of the mistakes made. Poor materials management may negatively influence the overall building process, including the timeline, quality, and money. According to current thinking, building material management in Somalia is presently considered ineffective. Also, is a severe shortage of standardized building materials management systems in Somalia's medium and small-scale construction sectors, one of the country's most significant difficulties? Also, effective planning and communication are to keep costs low, order errors to a minimum, and the possibility that the item will be on-site when required at the lowest possible price. Continuous communication and providing all necessary information in clear terms may help avoid mistakes.

1.0. Introduction.

Materials management is vital in managing projects as materials contribute more than 60% of the total project cost. It also plays a crucial role because the success of every construction project relies heavily on having materials on time and at a reasonable price. Thus, it affects the overall project performance. Despite the importance of materials management for construction projects, construction contractors are still suffering from the loss of productivity, project delay, and cost overruns due to the absence of proper implementation of materials management. Major issues affect materials management activities, site logistics concerning materials handling and distribution, and ordering and delivery of materials to the construction site.

1.1. Problem Statement.

Somalia currently does not have a well-developed system for managing building materials and construction materials. Due to the complexities of the construction industry, some projects have suffered material and financial losses because of the mistakes made (Allen & Iano, 2019). The management of building materials, as well known, plays an essential role in boosting the productivity of construction projects. Poor materials management may negatively influence the overall building process, including the timeline, quality, and money. According to current thinking, building material management in Somalia is presently considered ineffective. There is a severe shortage of standardized building materials management systems in Somalia's SME's construction sectors, one of the country's most significant difficulties. Furthermore, other obstacles include a shortage of storage space, transportation difficulties, material cost overruns, and material damage/loss, to name a few

Of the problems. There has been no research undertaken in Somalia yet to investigate the practices and issues associated with construction material management in medium and small-scale residential projects. To improve current processes, it is necessary to identify the problems and develop a practical plan for addressing them.

1.2. Objectives of the Study.

The main objective of this research is to find out what causes problems related to materials Management and the current Materials management practices on SME's building construction sites in Somalia, and to assess how to establish significant problems related to materials management on the construction site in Somalia.

1.3. Scope and the Significance of the Study.

This research aims to increase the efficiency of managing materials on SME's building sites. On Somali construction sites, site supervisors, operational managers' ineffective resources, and time management are significant causes of worry. Workers are sometimes not entirely occupied for extended periods because construction materials are not delivered on time or previous work has not been completed correctly (Bankvall et al., 2010).

2.0. Literature Review.

2.1. Introduction:

Academics define material management and its relationship to the building sector (Patel & Vyas, 2011). Various meanings are, therefore, found in different sources. According to Patel and Vyas (2011), material management involves planning, identification, procurement, storage, receipt, and distribution of required materials. Okolie and Mba (2020) argue that the material management goal is ensuring appropriate supplies are in the required location at the right time,

In the right amounts. Accordingly, the duty of each sector, such as the supply management department, maybe address the flow of materials from the time of purchase, receiving, and keeping materials until utilization time; this is the foundation of material management.

As a result, Kasim (2011) indicates that an effective material management system is required. Aljohani et al. (2017) argue that the person controlling management materials should be aware of the business' objectives and ensure that the company pays the required amount for supplies. Every business aims to earn a profit. Thus, this study support that profit is the foundation of a company's existence; therefore, expenses should be lower than revenue while ensuring significant consumer expectations.

2.2. Building Construction Site's Materials Management:

According to Patel and Vyas (2011), materials management is a fundamental component of supply chain management, which designs and executes supply chains to fulfill a company's supply needs. Controlling and managing the material allocation is among the needs since it evaluates price, availability, quality, and distribution. This research realized that the material managers decide the number of materials needed and cost. The managers later arrange for stock replenishment, create inventory levels for every item, for instance, raw material, finished goods, or work in progress, and provide information and requirements to procurement operations and the supply chain as realized by this study too. According to Robinson and Malhotra (2005), materials management comprises material quality evaluation to fulfill client expectations. However, the management should adhere to the production schedule at the lowest possible cost.

2.3. Current Practices of Materials Management on Medium and Small Construction Sites.

According to Papadopoulos et al. (2016), an efficient and productive project results from an excellent supply chain under current materials management practices on medium and small construction sites. The present techniques involve (1) inventory management, (2) project planning, (3) kitting, (4) lighting evaluation, and (5) labor force.

Gido and Clements (2014) indicate that the effective management of materials is critical to successful execution. Organizing material is a crucial and necessary topic for any business, and it must be appropriately managed to guarantee the success of a project. Accordingly, material variations have four consequences: quantity delays, time delays, quality delays, and product delays.

2.4. Major Problems Related to Materials Management on the Construction Site.

According to Fugar and Agyakwah-Baah (2010), materials management may be classified into the following categories. The first part is the specification and measurement. This literature review reveals the procurement and buying procedure through which the order is sent to the supplier. Besides, analysis of the latter study reveals the delivery to the job site and the logistics of verifying the order, unloading, and storage on-site. Sears et al. (2015) show the payment administration and financial procedure; using the materials in the manufacturing process on the worksite and eliminating the trash. According to Sears et al. (2015), the main obstacles in purchasing and supplying materials are a failure of matching supplies with the ordering purchase, forgetting Ordering materials, having too many or too few materials, late or early arriving at the site, lack of JIT strategy? Insufficient training, adequate management, and a lack of effective communication b/w contractors.

3.0. Research Methodology.

3.1. Introduction.

This section gives more details about the research onion, offering the research direction. Methodological research may be defined using the onion method, which provides a series of steps in which the various ways of data collecting can be comprehended. Saunders et al. created the research onion in 2007 to emphasize the steps that a researcher needs to go through to create a successful method. The research technique tree may be likened to onion when seen differently.

Figure 3.1 Research Onion Framework

Research onion (Saunders et al., 2015, p.102)

3.2. Research Philosophy.

Understanding the scientific research paradigm is necessary for defining a scientific research philosophy. According to scientific research literature, to do sound scientific research, the researcher must deeply comprehend paradigms or worldviews, which give philosophical, theoretical, and methodological groundings. Paradigm philosophy studies philosophical paradigms, including interpretivism, positivism, and critical theory (Zukauskas, Vveinhardt, & Andriukaitien, 2018). The four components of a research paradigm are ontology, epistemological foundations, methodology, and inquiry methodologies.

3.3. Research Approach.

The researcher chose abductive reasoning from the rest of the research approaches. Beginning with an incomplete set of data and moving down the list, abductive reasoning may be used to arrive at the most likely explanation for a set of observations (Mirza et al., 2014). This kind of day-to-day decision-making is based on the best information available, which is often inadequate or wrong. Abductive reasoning is the logical process of making observations and choosing a hypothesis that best fits or explains those findings (Mirza et al., 2014).

3.4. Research Method.

Mixed research is defined as “combining quantitative and qualitative research methods, procedures, approaches, ideas, or language into a single study” (Schoonenboom & Johnson, 2017). This phase of mixed research involves determining the mixed goal of the study and formulating mixed research objectives, as well as determining the rationale for mixing quantitative and qualitative approaches. The purpose of the research and purposes for combining quantitative and qualitative approaches, and the mixed (i.e., collecting quantitative and qualitative data, analyzing the quantitative and qualitative data,

Legitimizing the data sets and mixed research findings, interpreting the mixed research findings, writing the mixed research report, reformulating the mixed research question) (Schoonenboom & Johnson, 2017). In a mixed-methods study, the researcher could blend quantitative and qualitative data in a meaningful way.

3.5. Data Collection.

Closed-ended and open-ended questionnaires, as well as interviews, were used extensively in this mixed-method study. Combining these various data collection strategies might improve data quality and reliability. To compare findings from qualitative and quantitative data sources, the researcher employed a convergent design as an assessor (Ivankova, Creswell, & Stick, 2006). Each kind of data is collected and analyzed with the same amount of work, allowing findings to be compared reasonably simply. Aside from a side-by-side comparison in a discussion, the results are compared using strategies like converting qualitative data into quantitative evaluations or displaying both types of data simultaneously. Example: The overall quality of treatment provided was examined using survey methodologies, while qualitative data was acquired to study patient experiences. The two forms of data may be used to make assumptions about the intervention and provide validation for one another.

3.6. Questionnaire, Interview design and Administration.

Questionnaires are doubtless one of the primary sources of obtaining data in any research endeavor. However, the critical point is that when designing a questionnaire, the researcher should ensure that it is valid, reliable, and unambiguous (Koponen, Mäki-Opas, & Tolonen, 2011).

Overall, questionnaires were divided into three types: 1- closed-ended (or structured) questionnaires 2- open-ended (or unstructured) questionnaires 3-

A mixture of closed-ended and open-ended questionnaires. Closed-ended questionnaires provide the inquirer with quantitative or numerical data and open-ended questionnaires with qualitative or text information (Koponen, Mäki-Opas, & Tolonen, 2011). In this regard, the researcher divided questionnaires into seven basic question types: quantity or information, category, list or multiple choice, scale, ranking, and open-ended. Generally, a questionnaire uses one or several types of these question forms.

3.7. Participants and Sampling.

The time, money, and effort required to choose a representative sample of the study population must be considered. The researcher may learn more about a subset of the target population by using a sampling approach. The study's participants (over the age of 18) were recruited via family members and friends of the participants. As a result, the researcher is only interested in hearing from Somali residents employed in the construction business. Schreuder, Gregoire, and Weyer (2001) advised that a minimum sample size be utilized for each sample category. Non-probability convenience sampling was employed to arrive at a final sample size of participants for the study. Research has proved time and time again that using larger samples reduces the risk that findings may be extrapolated to the whole population. Research now uses a sample size that allows for a high number of participants with a small margin of error, which is beneficial. Non-probability convenience sampling was utilized in this study due to the challenges in recruiting participants (Schreuder, Gregoire, & Weyer, 2001). Non-probability convenience sampling is often used since it is cheap and straightforward to get (Schreuder, Gregoire, & Weyer, 2001). Researchers may use non-probability convenience sampling to quickly and cheaply acquire large amounts of data.

3.8. Data Analysis and ethic consideration.

Mixed methods research is a relatively recent technique to scientific investigation that combines quantitative and qualitative methodologies. Obtaining and interpreting quantitative as well as qualitative data. The iterative mixed analysis combines quantitative and qualitative methods into a single framework (representing analytical decisions that occur before and during the study). Triangulation, complementarity, development, initiation, and expansion are examples of pragmatism, transformative-emancipatory, and other mixed-methods research paradigms (O’Cathain, Murphy, & Nicholl, 2010). Iterative mixed analysis was done in several ways: simultaneously (i.e., not sequentially), sequentially (i.e., qualitative research comes before quantitative analysis, and the results of one phase influence the results of the next), or more than two phases (i.e., iteratively). Simple, mixed analytic results are possible, but more sophisticated research with limited interaction before data interpretation is possible. The mixed-methods design and mixed analysis may be connected (e.g., sequential mixed analysis techniques used for sequential mixed methods strategies).

4.0. Result Presentation.

4.1. Respondents General Information.

Table [4.1] – Respondents General Information.

Field of Business	Frequency	Cumulative (F)	Total	Percentage
Site Manager	19	19	100	19.0%
Architect	11	30	100	11.0%
Project Manager	15	45	100	15.0%
Builder	16	61	100	16.0%
Quantity surveyor	17	78	100	17.0%
Contractor	20	98	100	20.0%
other	2	100	100	2.0%

The above table 4.1: Respondents general information on field of operations within the construction firm the first part of the research questions established the participants' position in their various construction firms. The majority of the participants are contractors represented by 20%, followed by site managers represented by 19%, and the third-highest participants are quantity surveyors represented by 17%. Other participants represented by builders represented by 16%, project managers represented by 15%, and architecture described by 11%.

Table 4.2: Years of experiences

Years of Experience	Respondents	CF	Total	Percentage
1– 5 years	36	36	100	36.0%
6 – 10 years	36	72	100	36.0%
11 – 15 years	16	88	100	16.0%
Over 16	12	100	100	12.0%

The above table 4.2 shows the response of the participants on their years of experience, which is quite diversified. From the answers, most of the participants, represented by 36%, have about 1-10 years of working experience

In their construction sites. However, a handful has 11-15 years of work experience rated by 16%, and the last groups have over 16 years of work experience rated by 12%.

Education Level	Respondents	CF	Total	Percentage
High School or below	11	11	100	11.0%
Bachelor	44	55	100	44.0%
Master	26	81	100	26.0%
PHD	14	95	100	14.0%
Others	5	100	100	5.0%

Table 4.3: Education level

The researcher sorted from the participants their level of education. The researcher noted that most of the participants are well learned. For instance, the majority of the participants represented by 44% are bachelor holders, followed by master holders represented by 26%, and the Ph.D. group was 14%. The minor groups were high school diplomas and other certifications rated by 14% and 5% of the participants.

4.2. Section B: Material Management Practices in Construction Sites

Table 4.4: Person in charge of different operations

Person in Charge	Frequency	CF	Total	Percentage
Project Manager	27	27	100	27.0%
Quantity Surveyor	18	45	100	18.0%
Architect	4	49	100	4.0%
Contractor	31	80	100	31.0%
Site Engineer	20	100	100	20.0%
Others	0	100	100	0.0%

The participants were asked the person in charge of managing construction materials in their respective construction sites. Hence, the majority of the participants represented by 31% affirmed that contractors are in charge of overseeing construction materials. The second groups' persons in charge of construction material management are the project managers represented by 27%, site engineers represented by 20%, and quantity surveyors represented by 18%. The minor groups of participants have the architects in charge of building construction's material management.

Person Responsible	Frequency	CF	Total	Percent age
Project Manager	28	28	100	28.0%
Quantity Surveyor	18	46	100	18.0%
Architect	9	55	100	9.0%
Contractor	30	85	100	30.0%
Site Engineer	15	100	100	15.0%
Others	0	100	100	0.0%

Table 4.5: Person responsible in various departments

The participants were asked to state the person responsible for purchasing materials in their construction firm. The majority of the participants asserted that contractors and project managers are in charge of buying materials in their construction firm, represented by 30% and 28%, respectively. The third and fourth-largest groups confirmed that quantity surveyors and site engineers are responsible for purchasing materials described by 18% and 15%, respectively. The minor groups noted that architects are responsible for purchases represented by about 9%.

Figure 4.1: Type of purchases incurred during budgeting

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The participants were asked which method they apply in purchasing materials. As such, the majority of the participants, represented by 81%, suggested that the person in charge of building construction materials undertake the bulk purchases. In comparison, a handful represented by 19% makes in-piece purchases.

Figure 4.2: Agreement on single purchase or bulk purchases

The participants were asked to note if their firm conducted a market survey before purchasing materials. Thus, the majority of the participants represented by 80% affirmed that they show a market survey before purchase. In comparison, 20% suggested that their firms do not do any market research before purchases.

Figure 4.3: Type of market survey conducted before purchases

Figure 4.3: Type of market survey conducted before purchases.

Figure 4.2 summarizes the participants' responses that sorted to establish how participants assess the building construction materials. Majority of the participants, represented by 40%, suggested that they do testing of the construction materials followed by those that make selection represented by 36%. At the same time, the minor groups measure the materials, described by 24%.

4.3. Section C: Problems Related to Material Management

Table 4.6: Percentage (%) of the problems related to material management

Percentage (%) of the Problems Related To Material Management							
	Sample	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Strongly Agree	Agree	Sum
Lack of paper work planning and scheduling	100	11.0	8.0	18.0	30.0	33.0	63.0
Cash flow problems to contractor due to delayed payments	100	10.0	12.0	15.0	32.0	31.0	63.0
Late delivery of ordered materials	100	9.0	10.0	20.0	30.0	33.0	63.0
Damage to materials during transportation to the site	100	12.0	7.0	14.0	34.0	33.0	67.0

Over ordering of materials		12.0	10.0	15.0	31.0	32.0	63.0
Material shortage during construction and sudden alternation price of materials	100	11.0	10.0	13.0	34.0	32.0	66.0
Usage of material without systematic control	100	11.0	11.0	15.0	31.0	32.0	63.0
Change in material specifications during construction	100	10.0	11.0	17.0	32.0	30.0	62.0
Insufficient storage space	100	15.0	20.0	21.0	20.0	24.0	44.0
Improper handling of materials at side	100	12.0	16.0	19.0	26.0	27.0	53.0
Poor quality of materials	100	11.0	12.0	17.0	31.0	29.0	60.0
Use of incorrect materials	100	15.0	25.0	21.0	19.0	20.0	39.0
Poor use of advanced software	100	16.0	25.0	20.0	18.0	21.0	39.0
Theft of materials from site	100	11.0	13.0	29.0	20.0	27.0	47.0
There is material management problem due to the weather condition in construction site	100	16.0	15.0	16.0	27.0	26.0	53.0

The above table summarized the participants' responses based on the problems related to building construction materials and management they experienced in their firms. Most of the participants' responses, represented by 67%, affirmed that their primary problem is harmful materials during transportation to the site. However, another largest group, represented by 66% of the participants, noted that material shortage during construction and sudden alternation price of materials is another problem. Besides, a large group represented by 63% consented that the

Following are their construction management problems. The problem includes lack of paperwork planning and scheduling, cash flow problems to the contractor due to delayed payments, late delivery of ordered materials, over-ordering of materials, and material usage without systematic control. Another group represented by 60% noted that their problem includes the change in material specifications during construction. However, according to the participants, some of the minor problems described by 39%, 44%, and 47% include the use of faulty materials & poor use of advanced software, insufficient storage space, and theft of materials from the site.

4.4. Section D: Percentage of the Solutions to Problems Associated with Material Management.

Table 4.7: Percentage (%) of the solutions to problems associated with material management

Percentage (%) of the Solutions to Problems Associated with Material Management							
	Sample	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Strongly Agree	Agree	Sum
Timely placing of orders for materials and Proper materials delivery	100	12.0	11.0	17.0	34.0	26.0	60.0
Ensuring proper planning, monitoring, and control	100	9.0	11.0	13.0	32.0	35.0	67.0
Complete quality records of materials	100	11.0	9.0	14.0	31.0	35.0	66.0
Proper materials handling	100	12.0	10.0	10.0	35.0	33.0	68.0
Use of advanced software	100	13.0	9.0	16.0	31.0	31.0	62.0
Provision of adequate storage material	100	11.0	13.0	20.0	20.0	27.0	47.0
Proper usage of material	100	11.0	14.0	19.0	31.0	25.0	56.0

Use of advanced software	100	13.0	9.0	16.0	31.0	31.0	62.0
Provision of adequate storage material	100	11.0	13.0	20.0	20.0	27.0	47.0
Proper usage of material	100	11.0	14.0	19.0	31.0	25.0	56.0
Established material management system to be used	100	10.0	13.0	15.0	31.0	31.0	62.0
Attention to weather conditions	100	14.0	10.0	13.0	31.0	32.0	63.0
Make the store safe from theft and vandalism	100	13.0	10.0	11.0	31.0	35.0	66.0

The above table summarized the participants' responses based on the solutions to problems associated with material management in their firms. From the participants' response, the majority of the participants, represented by 68%, affirmed that proper material handling of the material is an excellent solution to most of the problems such as damage to materials during transportation to the site, over-ordering of materials, usage of material without systematic control, improper handling of materials at the site, and theft of materials from the site.

Other solutions to the problems associated with material management on their firms included ensuring proper planning, monitoring, and control. Secondly, other ways include complete quality records of materials, the use of advanced software, an established material management system, and making the store safe from theft and vandalism.

5.0. Discussions.

5.1. Introduction.

The first is assessing the building construction sites' materials management in Somalia. The second part is the assessment and establishment of the current practices of materials management on medium and small construction sites in Somalia. Thirdly, is assessing and establishing the significant problems related to materials management on the construction site in Somalia. The last inquiry demonstrates how to improve material management practices in the construction site in Somalia and light the rest of the world.

5.2. Result Discussion.

The first part of the objectives aimed at assessing the building construction sites' materials management in Somalia. The study established that numerous small companies in the informal sector are neither VAT-registered nor run pay-as-you-go systems. The SME is project-driven and is constantly looking for ways to cut expenses and save money, and they are more likely to get business based on a low bid price than their technology (Donyavi & Flanagan, 2009). Bids are based on resource estimation based on prior project knowledge and expertise, and cash flow is critical for timely payment of suppliers and ensuring future material supply. Materials are purchased just in time to assist with cash flow and storage constraints. With bulk purchasing because it saves cost. However, site design for material offloading and storage is often a haphazard procedure. Delivery timetables are often random, resulting in wasteful labor use. The supply chain for construction is a handy method of expressing a sequential linear supply chain, yet the supply chain is lengthy, complicated, and often not consecutive.

6.0. Conclusion and Recommendations.

6.1. Conclusion.

Materials account for about 60% of the overall project expenditure. A project's success depends on receiving resources on time and within budget. The widespread success of the initiative is jeopardized. Several construction companies have suffered productivity losses, project delays, and cost overruns due to poor material management. Somalia has no system in place to track and control construction materials now. The building industry's complexity has led to material and monetary losses. Better material management in construction may boost productivity. Poor material management may influence the construction process, including time, quality, and money. Somalia's construction material management is currently inadequate. Getting supplies on time takes a lot of labor. Material supply delays or shortages are likely due to changes made during material take-off. Changing the timetable could help. Earlier orders may have been late. Changes in design may cause delays if some materials need less material than others.

6.2. Recommendations.

The research could not make causal conclusions since the sample was cross-sectional. Longitudinal research may be the most effective method for mixed-methods quantitative analysis. Secondly, this study proposes focusing on specific SMEs and their management rather than the whole of Somalia nation. Although SMEs face comparable difficulties, the results gained may not apply to different samples gathered elsewhere. So we are recommending to do engineering further studies in this section to get more solutions for the current problems.

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